

Mathematical Modelling and Computer Simulation of Bio-Similar Processes and Systems

Kateryna Hazdiuk, PHD-student

*Department of Computer Technology, Yuriy Fedkovych Chernivtsi National University
Kotsyubynsky 2, 58012 Chernivtsi, Ukraine*

k.gazdiuk@chnu.edu.ua

Abstract — The basis of computer modelling of any process or system is mathematical models that describe those objects. The movable cellular automata method allows to describe the object of modelling in the form of a set of an interacting discrete elements (automata). Each automaton simulates a circular (for a two-dimensional case) or spherical (for a three-dimensional case) particle of an object and it is small compared to the linear dimensions of the system, and also it describes a set of characteristic parameters that control the behaviour of the system, depending on the type of element in the simulated structure. The dynamics of the automata set is determined by the functions of their interaction and the rules according to which their states change. The work is devoted to finding and constructing those interaction functions.

Keywords — cellular automata, bio-similar processes, bio-similar systems, mathematical modelling, computer simulation, off-lattice models.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, computer simulation is one of the most powerful tools for scientific research and engineering applications. This makes it possible not only to reproduce the results of real experiments with a fairly high degree of accuracy, but also to reduce financial costs and eliminate dangerous precedents. Moreover, in some cases, there is no alternative to computer models at all.

Simulation of biological processes and systems is one of the most relevant and promising areas of research [1]. Unlike examples of modelling physical phenomena, the mechanisms of many bioprocesses are currently unknown. Such issues include, in particular: the processes of self-organization and evolution of living matter [2, 3]; mechanisms of synergetic cooperation in colonies of unicellular organisms and their organization in the form of multicellular systems accompanied by cell differentiation; self-organization of different signal flows in neural subsystems of organisms, etc. Computer simulation is not limited to the study of interaction mechanisms, but also explores methods of their application in various fields of science, while helping to test hypotheses and theoretical assumptions in practice, as well as to identify new phenomena in the behaviour of studied biosimilar processes and structures.

Given the importance of such research, the study of the mechanisms of dynamics of biosystems is a topical issue, for example analogues of biosystems (tissues, organs, cells and organisms in general), created artificially (simulated in

software or robotic mechanisms). Such systems can be called distributed, bearing in mind that, unlike the vast majority of modern computer technology developed by man, they do not have any central control element that would be responsible for making all decisions. The distributed nature of self-organization mechanisms makes them particularly resistant to various failures and interventions of external factors, because without a vulnerable management, it is not easy to suffer damage that would lead to the collapse of the whole system of self-organization as a whole.

The basis of computer simulation of any process or system is mathematical models that describe these objects. The first mathematical models of biosimilar processes were based on ordinary differential equations, differential equations with partial derivatives and systems of differential equations [4]. It is clear that the processes described by such models were trivial, with a number of limitations and assumptions, and practical application did not allow to obtain acceptable results.

The next step in modelling biosystems was the transition to discrete-continuous models, with a continuous time variable but a discrete spatial one. Such models include the Potts model, L-systems [5], models that describe cells with complex geometric shapes involving the theory of elasticity, and so on. However, differential equations were still used to describe processes, and therefore all the problems of numerical methods for solving differential equations, such as the accumulation of rounding errors, the complexity of describing and solving in multidimensional cases, etc., were remained open.

A natural stage in the development of mathematical and computer simulation of bio-processes is the transition to discrete models [6]. The discrete modelling tools that using to build models of biological objects and their dynamics are quite diverse: from the construction of simple agent models to simulation algorithms of complex models that reflect the individual components of the respective processes or systems. One of such modelling approaches is the cellular automata method (CA), and asynchronous stochastic models are most important in modelling various biological phenomena because they reflect the fact that in nature most processes are stochastic rather than deterministic. However, in the classical CA the array of cells is presented in the form of a static regular lattice (lattice models), which complicates the modelling of time-varying structures, therefore, to study the dynamics of the structure of the simulated space, the method of movable cellular automata (MCA, off-lattice method of modelling) was chosen.

Computer modelling of the dynamics of biosimilar structures is a complex process because it requires a relationship between models of self-organizing mechanisms and the dynamics of the simulated space that occurs during certain biosimilar processes (for example, growth, division, movement, etc.). Classical modelling tools, which have proven themselves well in self-organization models, have low efficiency in tasks related to the dynamics of the simulated space. Therefore, most of the existing models used to study such self-organizing mechanisms reflect the processes occurring in static structures and model, for example, the shape of the cell surface, despite the processes occurring in it [7, 8]. The latter precludes a direct study of the feedback between these self-organizing mechanisms, and the processes themselves.

II. METHOD OF SIMULATION

An MCA is a method that originated in the computational mechanics of a deformed solid. It is based on a discrete approach and combines the advantages of the method of classical cellular automata and the method of discrete elements. The precondition for the method was the difficulties that arose in modeling the destruction of the material, in particular the generation of damage, crack propagation and fragmentation, as well as mixing of the substance [9, 10, 11]. An important advantage of the MCA method is the ability to model not only complex physicochemical processes, but also processes in general, where there is an arbitrary change in the coordinates of the components of the simulated objects in space.

In the MCA method, the modeling object is described as a set of n interacting discrete elements (automata). Each automaton simulates a circular (for a two-dimensional case) spherical particle of an object and is small compared to the linear dimensions of the system, and describes a set of characteristic parameters that control the behavior of the system, depending on the type of element in the simulated structure.

The dynamics of the set of automata is determined by the functions of their interaction and the rules according to which their states change. In general, the set of mobile cellular automata can be represented as $M = \{A, Q\}$, where A is the set describing the structure of the MCA; Q is a set of local operators that describe the principles of application of MCA interaction functions.

$$A = \{a_i(s_i, c_i, N_i, p_i) \mid i = \overline{1, n}, n \in \mathbb{N}, \\ s_i \in S, c_i \in C, N_i \in Ne, p_i \in P\}; \quad (1)$$

$$Q = \{q_1(A, F), q_2(A, F), \dots, q_m(A, F)\}, m \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (2)$$

In the structure (1) $i = \overline{1, n}$, ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) is a finite number of MCA, which indicates the ordinal number of the automaton in the structure and characterizes its unique name; $S = \{1, 2, \dots, j\}$, ($j \in \mathbb{N}$) is a finite set of MCA states, which can be denoted both by integers and symbolically; $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\} = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$ (for the two-dimensional case), and $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\} = \{(x_1, y_1, z_1), (x_2, y_2, z_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n, z_n)\}$ (for the three-dimensional case), $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $x_i, y_i, z_i \in \mathbb{R}$ ($i = \overline{1, n}$) is the set of coordinates of the corresponding MCA on the plane and in space, respectively; $Ne = \{N_1, N_2, \dots, N_n\}$, where $N_i = \{N_{i1}, N_{i2}, \dots, N_{i6} \mid N_{ij} = \overline{1, n}, N_{ij} \neq i\}$ (for the two-dimensional case), $N_i = \{N_{i1}, N_{i2}, \dots, N_{i12} \mid N_{ij} = \overline{1, n}, N_{ij} \neq i\}$ (for the three-

dimensional case) is a set containing the indices of adjacent automata for the corresponding MCA; $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_l\}$, ($l \in \mathbb{N}$) is a set of additional parameters of the MCA, which is entered if necessary, but may be empty.

The evolution of such a system in space and time is determined by the equations of motion described by local operators (2).

In the set (2) $q_p(A, F)$ ($p = \overline{1, m}$) are local interaction operators, which, depending on the state of the automaton, the state of its neighbor and the interaction function F at a given time t , allow to calculate the state of the automaton and its dynamics at the next time $t + 1$. The interaction functions F can be both elementary (imitation of thermal oscillations, mutual repulsion or mutual attraction, etc.) and compositions of elementary functions.

It should be noted that automata can acquire arbitrary coordinates in space when simulating by the MCA method. Thus, when building a model there is a need to move from a static grid concept, which is characteristic of classical automatic methods to a new neighborhood concept. To ensure the adequacy of the models, automata must be able to change their neighbors by switching the state of pairs. Compared to the classical cellular automata method, in the MCA method not only the automaton itself, but also the connections between them can be switched.

To ensure the bistability of automata, two pairs of states (relationships) are introduced: bound (hard or weak) or unbound. The neighbors should be searched and interaction rules should be described due to the local operators in each iteration step for every automaton.

Entering a new state type requires a new parameter to be used as a criterion for switching to the "linked" state. The initial structure is formed by establishing the properties of a certain relationship between each pair of adjacent elements. Thus, the change in the state of coupling of a pair is determined by the relative motion of automata, and the medium formed by such pairs can be called a bistable medium.

To determine the state of the connection between pairs of automata, a neighborhood criterion (or a criterion for connecting and disconnecting communication) is introduced. In general, this criterion is formed based on the properties of the simulated system. This can be a given distance between the centers of automata or belonging to some environment of a given automaton, and more complex neighborhood conditions that involve the performance of several factors simultaneously (relative distance, type of automaton, type of neighbor, etc.). In the simplest case, the criterion of neighborhood is the distance between the centers of the automata, i.e. neighbors are those elements between which the distance is the smallest or does not exceed a given relative value. It should also be noted that the number of related elements (neighbors) in this approach is fixed. In particular, for the two-dimensional case, the automaton chooses 6 nearest neighbors, and for the three-dimensional case – 12, which corresponds to the tight packing of circles on the plane and balls in space.

It should be noted that for automata that are at the boundary of the structure, the boundary conditions should be taken into

account. Also, in modeling process it may be necessary to build a structure with trigonal, tetragonal, octagonal, etc. the neighborhood scheme for a two-dimensional case, and hexagonal or icosahedral neighborhood scheme for a three-dimensional case. For this purpose, it is possible to enter zero values in the set of data structures N_i , thus indicating the presence of the automaton not 6 or 12 neighbors, but a smaller number of them.

III. INTERACTIONS FUNCTIONS

As noted above, the dynamics of a set of automata is determined by the functions of their interaction, which can be both elementary functions and combinations of elementary functions. We describe the basic elementary functions of interactions.

f_0 is the simplest function that simulates the thermal oscillations of the MCA, i.e. the random shift of the MCA coordinates in an arbitrary direction. Let the automaton a_i at some point in time t has real coordinates in space (x_i, y_i, z_i) . Then under the influence of the function f_0 at the next point in time $t+1$ its coordinates will be determined by the formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} x_i^{t+1} &= x_i^t + r \sin \alpha \cos \varphi; \\ y_i^{t+1} &= y_i^t + r \sin \alpha \sin \varphi; \\ z_i^{t+1} &= z_i^t + r \cos \alpha. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here α and φ are the angles of shifting, $\alpha = \pi \text{rand}(180)/180$, $\varphi = 2\pi \text{rand}(360)/360$; r is the amount of displacement, $r = r_{\max} \text{rand}(m)/m$; r_{\max} is the maximum possible shear distance during thermal oscillations; $\text{rand}(m)$ is a function that returns a random integer from a given interval, $0 \leq \text{rand}(m) \leq m$, m is an integer selected for each model empirically. For the two-dimensional case, formulas (3) are rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_i^{t+1} &= x_i^t + r \cos \varphi; \\ y_i^{t+1} &= y_i^t + r \sin \varphi. \end{aligned}$$

f_1 is a function that performs the operation of repulsion of two RCA when they overlap. This function allows you to simulate the compression of the environment.

Consider two automata a_i and a_j ($i \neq j$), which occur in the corresponding states $s_i = k$ and $s_j = l$. It should be noted that the states of automata can be the same, it means that $k = l$ is allowed. In the graphical representation of the model, automata with different states are represented by circles (for the two-dimensional case) or spheres (for the three-dimensional case) of different colors and radii. Let r_i and r_j be the radii of automata a_i and a_j , respectively, at time t . To ensure the incompressibility of the medium, when the automata converge at a distance less than $r_i + r_j$, the MCA must be repelled. Then, as a result of applying the function f_1 , the coordinates of the automata at time $t + 1$ are calculated by formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} x_i^{t+1} &= \frac{x_i^t - \lambda x_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad x_j^{t+1} = \frac{x_j^t - \lambda x_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \\ y_i^{t+1} &= \frac{y_i^t - \lambda y_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad y_j^{t+1} = \frac{y_j^t - \lambda y_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \\ z_i^{t+1} &= \frac{z_i^t - \lambda z_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad z_j^{t+1} = \frac{z_j^t - \lambda z_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\lambda = \min \left\{ \frac{|(r_i + r_j) - d|}{2d + r_i + r_j}, \frac{|(r_i + r_j) - d|}{(2d + r_i + r_j)n} \right\} - \quad (5)$$

shear coefficient;

$d = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2 + (z_i - z_j)^2}$ is the distance between the centers of the balls that mimic the automata a_i and a_j . Obviously, for the two-dimensional case $z_i = z_j = 0$.

It should be noted that the shear coefficient is quite small relative to the radii of the spheres. This is due to the fact that if the overlap of two adjacent automata is removed at once, there may be even more overlap with other neighbors, and if this is done in several iterations, not only the automata of this pair will be gradually repelled, but the whole structure will be uncompressed.

f_2 is a function that attracts two MCA. The function allows to simulate the condensed state of the environment and prevents the appearance of voids inside the structure. Functions f_1 and f_2 ensure the stability of the volume of internal environments. If the automata a_i and a_j move away from each other by a distance exceeding $r_i + r_j + \delta_{\max}$, where δ_{\max} is the maximum allowable distance between two MCA, then they must be brought closer. Then, as a result of applying the function f_2 , the coordinates of the centers of automata at the next time will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x_i^{t+1} &= \frac{x_i^t + \lambda x_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad x_j^{t+1} = \frac{x_j^t + \lambda x_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \\ y_i^{t+1} &= \frac{y_i^t + \lambda y_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad y_j^{t+1} = \frac{y_j^t + \lambda y_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \\ z_i^{t+1} &= \frac{z_i^t + \lambda z_j^t}{1 + \lambda}; \quad z_j^{t+1} = \frac{z_j^t + \lambda z_i^t}{1 + \lambda}; \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where λ is a shifting coefficient, which is calculated by the formula (5).

Obviously, for the two-dimensional case $z_i = z_j = 0$.

f_3 is a function that performs the alignment of some MCA relative to the same type of neighbors. This simulates the local formation of fragments of threads. Suppose that random automatons of the same type are chosen at random: a_k and one of its neighbors a_i . Next, among the other neighbors, the automaton a_j is chosen, which has the same type, and there is an interaction, which as a result of applying the function f_3 aligns the k -th MCA with respect to two neighbors with indices i and j . The coordinates of the center of the automaton a_k (x_k, y_k, z_k) are calculated by formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} x_k^{t+1} &= \frac{2x_k^t + \lambda x_i^t + \lambda x_j^t}{2(1 + \lambda)}; \\ y_k^{t+1} &= \frac{2y_k^t + \lambda y_i^t + \lambda y_j^t}{2(1 + \lambda)}; \\ z_k^{t+1} &= \frac{2z_k^t + \lambda z_i^t + \lambda z_j^t}{2(1 + \lambda)}; \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where λ is a shifting coefficient, which is calculated by the formula (5).

Obviously, for the two-dimensional case $z_i = z_j = z_k = 0$.

f_4 is an operation that adds an automaton to a cell-automaton field. This operation is necessary for modeling the growth of biosystems. When new automata appear on the cellular-automata field, they are assigned the index of the automaton of type zero, if such exist in structure (1), the type and coordinates are redefined according to the conditions of the problem. If such automatons do not exist, then the automaton that appears receives the next unoccupied index. Neighborhood ties are also

being built right away. The appearance of the automaton can occur both due to the interaction of two adjacent elements, and independently at certain intervals.

f_5 is an operation that removes an automaton. When modeling biosimilar phenomena, it may be necessary to remove the automaton. In this case, it is assigned a zero type, which corresponds to a sphere of zero radius, and all its neighborhood connections are destroyed, which means that it cannot interact with any automaton. New automata are being sought for vending automata that were its neighbors.

$$f_5: a_i^t(s_i^t, c_i^t, N_i^t, p_i^t) \rightarrow a_i^{t+1}(s_i^{t+1}, c_i^{t+1}, N_i^{t+1}, p_i^{t+1}),$$

$$s_i^{t+1} = 0, k \in S, k \neq s_i^t, N_i^{t+1} = \emptyset. \quad (8)$$

f_6 is a function that changes the state of an automaton. Often there is a need not only to move the automaton in space, but also to change its properties, which are described by the state of the automaton. This is one of the main operations in cellular automata modeling, when the state of the automaton changes when interacting with neighboring automata, giving it other properties. When performing such an operation on some automaton a_i in structure (1), the component s_i changes its value at the next moment in time.

$$f_6: a_i^t(s_i^t, c_i^t, N_i^t, p_i^t) \rightarrow a_i^{t+1}(s_i^{t+1}, c_i^{t+1}, N_i^{t+1}, p_i^{t+1}), s_i^{t+1} =$$

$$k, k \in S, k \neq s_i^t. \quad (9)$$

It should be noted that not only automata, but also the connections between them can be of a certain type (for example, weak or rigid). The type of neighborhood, as well as the type of automaton affects the interaction functions. Yes, if the connections in the neighborhood, for example, are weak, the interaction between the automata may not occur at all. This is due to the fact that sometimes there is a need to interact with only two neighboring automata, and according to a fixed scheme, the neighborhood is 6 (for the two-dimensional case) or 12 (for the three-dimensional case).

IV. EXAMPLES OF SIMULATION

Examples of the use of these functions are discussed in detail in previous works [12-14]. Generalization of the research results and computer simulation are presented in the Table I.

TABLE I
GENERALIZATION OF THE INTERACTION FUNCTION APPLICATION AND COMPUTER SIMULATION DIFFERENT BIO-LIKE SYSTEMS AND PROCESSES

No	Object of research	Applicable interaction functions	Figure with computer simulation Result
1	Worm-like movement	f_0, f_1, f_2, f_6	Fig. 1 a)
2	Amoeba-like locomotion	$f_0, f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5$	Fig. 1 b)
3	Self-regeneration process	f_4, f_5, f_6	Fig. 1 c)
4	Self-replication process	f_4, f_5, f_6	Fig. 1 d)
5	Biological engine	f_0, f_1, f_2, f_3	Fig. 1 e)

Fig. 1. Example of the computer simulation: a) worm-like movement; b) amoeba-like locomotion; c) self-regeneration process; d) self-replication process; e) biological engine.

V. CONCLUSION

This article presents a description of the MCA method applied to the modeling of biosimilar processes and structures.

As a result of the conducted researches the mathematical model of MCA in formalism of the theory of sets where each element of structure reflects corresponding characteristics or properties of MCA-model is described; the main schemes of MCA neighborhood, which are selected according to the properties of the model, are considered.

There is also a description of the basic elementary functions of interactions and their possible parameters. The dynamics of the model is determined by the established elementary interaction functions and their combinations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Hill, Biological Engineering, Callisto Reference, 2015, p. 286.
- [2] Sven A. Brueckner, Giovanna Di Marzo Serugendo, Anthony Karageorgos, Radhika Nagpal. Engineering Self-Organising Systems: Methodologies and Applications, Berlin: Springer, 2005, p. 297.
- [3] Scott Camazine, Jean-Louis Deneubourg, Nigel R. Franks, James Sneyd, Guy Theraulaz, & Eric Bonabeau. Self-Organization in Biological Systems, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2003, p. 562.
- [4] Kolmogorov, A. Study of the diffusion equation coupled to an increase in mass and its application to a problem in biology / A. Kolmogorov, I. Petrovsky, N. Piskunov // Bull Uni Moskou Ser Int A1. – 1937. – no. 6. – 26 pp
- [5] Lindenmayer, A. Locally Generated Colourings of Hexagonal Cell Division Patterns: Application to Retinal Cell Differentiation. In Lindenmayer systems: Impacts on theoretical computer science, computer graphics, and developmental biology, / A. Lindenmayer, Z. Tuza; Ed. by G. Rozenberg, A. Salomaa. — Berlin: Springer-Verlag, 1992. – Pp. 333–350.
- [6] Politopoulos, I. (11 September 2007). "Review and Analysis of Agent-based Models in Biology" (PDF). Archived from the original (PDF) on 27 July 2011.
- [7] Shao D, Levine H, Rappel WJ. Coupling actin flow, adhesion, and morphology in a computational cell motility model. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences. 2012; 109(18):6851–6856.
- [8] Niculescu I, Textor J, de Boer RJ (2015) Crawling and Gliding: A Computational Model for Shape-Driven Cell Migration. PLoS Comput Biol 11(10): e1004280.
- [9] S. G. Psakhie, Y. Horie, S. Yu. Korostelev, A. Yu. Smolin, A. I. Dmitriev, E. V. Shilko, and S. V. Alekseev, "Method of Movable Cellular Automata as a Tool for Simulation within the Framework of Mesomechanics," Russian Physics Journal, 38(11), 1995.
- [10] S. G. Psakhie, Y. Horie, G. P. Ostermeyer, S. Yu. Korostelev, A. Yu. Smolin, E. V. Shilko, A. I. Dmitriev, S. Blatnik, M. Spegel, and S. Zavsek, Movable Cellular Automata Method for Simulating Materials with Mesostructure", Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics, 37(1), 2001 pp. 311–334.
- [11] V. L. Popov and S. G. Psakhie, "Theoretical Principles of Modelling Elastoplastic Media by Movable Cellular Automata Method. I. Homogeneous Media," Physical Mesomechanics, 4(1), 2001 pp. 15–25.
- [12] Hazdiuk Ye. P., Zhikharevich V. V., Nikitina O.M., Ostapov S. E. The unicellular microorganisms "Amoeba Proteus" locomotion simulation with the use of movable cellular automata method // Prikladnaya Diskretnaya Matematika. 2018. № 42. C. 104–119. DOI: 10.17223/20710410/42/8ПДМ. http://journals.tsu.ru/pdm/en/&journal_page=archive&id=1803&article_id=39876
- [13] Zhikharevich V. Simulation of bio-like systems and processes using movable cellular automata / Volodymyr Zhikharevich, Kateryna Hazdiuk and Serhiy Ostapov [Electronic resource] // Proceedings of the Second International Workshop on Computer Modeling and Intelligent Systems (CMIS-2019), Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine, April 15-19, 2019 / [eds.: D. Luengo, S. Subbotin, P. Arras, Ye. Bodyanskiy, K. Henke, I. Izonin, V. Levashenko, V. Lytvynenko, A. Parkhomenko, A. Pester, N. Shakhovska, A. Sharpanskykh, G. Tabunshchyyk, C. Wolff, H.-D. Wuttke, E. Zaitseva]. – P. 664-673. – (CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Vol. 2353). – Access mode: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2353/paper63.pdf>
- [14] Zhikharevich V. Software for simulation of bio-like systems and processes using movable cellular automata / Volodymyr Zhikharevich, Kateryna Hazdiuk and Serhiy Ostapov [Electronic resource] // Proceedings of The Third International Workshop on Computer Modeling and Intelligent Systems (CMIS-2020), Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine, April 27-May 1, 2020/ [Edited by Sergey Subbotin]. – P. 514-525. – (CEUR Workshop Proceedings, Vol. 2353). – Access mode: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2608/paper39.pdf>